

Synthesis of amino acid derivatives of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole

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Abstract : The reaction of ethyl benzothiazole-2-yl-thioacetate and methyl benzothiazole-2-yl-thiopropionate with various amino acids in presence of alkali at 0–5 °C to form peptide has been described.

Keywords : Peptides, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole, amino acids.

Introduction

Benzothiazole derivatives have been extensively studied because of their broad spectrum of biological activities and industrial applications¹. The amino acids and their derivatives, are becoming increasingly important as the intermediates for pharmaceuticals and agro-chemicals^{2,3}. They play an outstanding role as growth promoters, hormones, ionophores, antibiotics, immune peptides and toxins^{4,5}. Some well known examples include D-phenylglycine and D-*p*-hydroxy phenylglycine as the building blocks for the antibiotics Ampicillin, respectively. Similarly, the L-valine act as a precursors for the immunodepressant cyclosporin A- and D-valine is useful in the production of Fluvalinate and a pyrethroid insecticides. Currently, it has been reported that 2'-benzothiazolylthioester of *N*-substituted alpha amino acids act as the versatile intermediate for synthesis of ACE inhibitors⁶. Therefore, in present study, we report the synthesis of peptides which may act as an intermediates for the synthesis of new drugs.

Results and discussion

The experimental route involved the reaction of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole **1** with ethyl chloroacetate and methyl α -chloropropionate in presence of triethylamine in dichloroethane to afford ethyl benzothiazole-2-yl-thioacetate **2** and methyl benzothiazole-2-yl-thiopropionate **3**. The structures of these compounds were ensured on the basis of IR and ¹H NMR. Compounds **2** and **3** showed characteristic absorption at 1737 cm⁻¹ and 1730 cm⁻¹ due to ester group respectively. The ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2** showed a triplet at δ 1.3 due to CH₃, a quartet at δ 4.15 due to OCH₂ and a singlet at δ 4.3 due to S-CH₂. The ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **3** exhibited a doublet at δ 1.1 due to CH₃, a singlet at δ 3.78 due to OCH₃ and a quartet at δ 4.15 due to CH. Further,

compounds **2** and **3** with various amino acids when employed in equimolar proportions at 0–5 °C in presence of 4 *N* NaOH to afforded the amino acid derivatives of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole, **4** and **5** respectively. The structures of the compounds **4** and **5** were assigned on the basis of IR and ¹H NMR spectral data. The presence of absorption band in the range of 1610–1740 cm⁻¹ confirmed the presence of carbonyl group of amide and carboxylic acid. The compounds **4** and **5** showed a singlet in the range δ 3.9–4.1 ppm due to -SCH₂ and a quartet between δ 4.0–4.3 ppm due to S-CH(CH₃) respectively. However, both the compounds **4** and **5** showed a broad singlets due to CONH protons in between δ 9–10 ppm and a singlet at δ 10–12.1 ppm due to COOH both exchangeable with D₂O. The synthetic route for peptides containing 2-mercaptobenzothiazole has been illustrated in Scheme 1. Further, these compounds with substitution pattern R' = H, CH₂CH₂CH₃, CH₂SH, have been recommended for screening of activities like Angiogenesis inhibitor, NMDA receptor glycine site agonist, Chemoprotective, Autoimmune disorders treatment as the promising compounds on the basis of PASS values⁷ (Table 3).

Scheme 1

Experimental

All m.p.s were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on Shimadzu IR-470 spectrophotometer (cm^{-1}) and ^1H NMR spectra were scanned on a Bruker Avance II 400 NMR spectrometer (chemical shifts in δ ppm) using TMS as an internal standard in DMSO. Purity of compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel G.

General procedure for the synthesis of esters of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole :

Ethyl benzothiazole-2-yl-thioacetate (2) :

The mixture of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (1) (50 mmol) and triethylamine (60 mmol) in dichloromethane (40 ml) was stirred at room temperature and ethyl chloroacetate was added dropwise and the reaction mixture stirred further for about 2 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue triturated with dil. HCl. The product obtained was recrystallized from methanol, m.p. 40 °C; yield (85%); IR (KBr) : 2900 (CH), 1737 (ester) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 1.3 (3H, t, J 7.5 Hz, ester CH_3), 4.15 (2H, q, J 7.5 Hz, OCH_2), 4.3 (2H, s, S-CH_2), 7.35 (1H, t, ArH), 7.5 (1H, t, ArH), 7.8 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, ArH), 8.05 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, ArH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$): δ 13.84, 34.50, 61.22, 120.98, 121.74, 124.43, 126.26, 134.63, 152.22, 165.27, 169.06; GC MS (m/z) : 253, 208, 180, 166, 108.

Table 1. Physical data of compounds 4a-e and 5a-e

Entry ^a	R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
4a	H	H	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	155	70
4b	H	CH_3	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	132	62
4c	H	CH_2Ph	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	147	59
4d	H	CH_2SH	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{S}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	162	58
4e	H	$\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	170	60
5a	CH_3	H	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	137	65
5b	CH_3	CH_3	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	146	72
5c	CH_3	CH_2Ph	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	159	62
5d	CH_3	CH_2SH	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{S}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	161	57
5e	CH_3	$\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{S}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	165	61

^aAll reactions were carried out on 0.1 mmol scale, at 0–5 °C.

The yields are determined by analytical method.

Methyl benzothiazole-2-yl-thiopropionate (3) :

The compound 3 was prepared by the procedure as mentioned for compound 2. b.p. 98 °C at 0.1 mm of Hg; yield (86%); IR (KBr) : 2900 (CH), 1730 (ester) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 1.1 (3H, d, J 7.5 Hz, CH_3), 3.78 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.15 (1H, q, J 7.5 Hz, $-\text{CH}$), 6.9–8.1 (4H, m, ArH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$): δ 34.23, 38.99, 55.52, 109.33, 114.49, 127.44, 128.87, 129.13, 129.46, 159.53, 172.64.

Table 2. Spectral data of compounds 4a-e and 5a-e

Entry	R	R'	IR (KBr)(cm^{-1})	^1H NMR (DMSO) (ppm)
4a	H	H	1713, 1674, 2503, 3300	3.6 (2H, s, NHCH_2COOH), 4.1 (2H, s, $\text{S-CH}_2\text{CONH}$), 7–7.35 (2H, m, ArH), 7.5–7.6 (1H, d, ArH), 7.7–7.8 (1H, d, ArH), 9.4 (1H, brs, CONH), 10.5 (1H, s, COOH)
4b	H	CH_3	1720, 1644, 2530, 3310	1.3 (3H, d, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{COOH}$), 4.2 (2H, s, SCH_2), 4.65 (1H, m, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_3)$), 7.1–7.4 (2H, m, ArH), 7.5–7.6 (1H, d, ArH), 7.7–7.8 (1H, d, ArH), 9.5 (1H, brs, CONH), 10.5 (1H, s, COOH)
4c	H	CH_2Ph	1709, 1650, 2410, 3420	3.1 (2H, d, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_2\text{Ph})\text{COOH}$), 4.05 (2H, s, SCH_2), 4.2 (1H, m, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_2\text{Ph})\text{COOH}$), 6.9–7.2 (2H, m, ArH), 7.3–7.6 (3H, m, ArH), 7.7–7.9 (4H, m, ArH), 9.7 (1H, brs, CONH), 9.9 (1H, s, COOH)
4d	H	CH_2SH	1713, 1680, 2503, 3436	2.7 (1H, s, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_2\text{SH})\text{COOH}$), 3.23 (2H, m, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_2\text{SH})$), 3.9 (2H, s, SCH_2), 4.3 (1H, m, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_2\text{SH})\text{COOH}$), 7.1–7.2 (1H, t, ArH), 7.5 (1H, t, ArH), 7.9 (1H, d, ArH), 8.1 (1H, d, ArH), 9.8 (1H, brs, CONH), 10.5 (1H, s, COOH)
4e	H	$\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_3$	1705, 1655, 2520, 3310	0.9 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.3–1.35 (4H, m, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 4.2 (2H, m, S-CH_2), 4.4 (1H, m, NHCH), 7.1–7.3 (2H, m, ArH), 7.5–7.7 (2H, m, ArH), 9.4 (1H, brs, CONH), 10.2 (1H, s, COOH)
5a	CH_3	H	1717, 1640, 2510, 3440	1.0 (3H, d, CH_3), 3.7 (2H, s, NHCH_2COOH), 4.1 (1H, q, $\text{S-CH}(\text{CH}_3)$), 7.1–7.2 (1H, t, ArH), 7.3–7.5 (1H, t, ArH), 7.6–7.8 (2H, m, ArH), 9.5 (1H, brs, CONH), 10.3 (1H, s, COOH)
5b	CH_3	CH_3	1720, 1646, 2500, 3410	1.05 (3H, d, CH_3), 1.2 (2H, d, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{COOH}$), 4.1 (1H, q, $\text{S-CH}(\text{CH}_3)$), 4.6 (1H, m, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{COOH}$), 7.2–7.4 (2H, m, ArH), 7.5 (1H, d, ArH), 7.6–7.7 (1H, d, ArH), 9.65 (1H, brs, CONH), 10.5 (1H, s, COOH)
5c	CH_3	CH_2Ph	1714, 1650, 2420, 3320	1.0 (3H, d, CH_3), 3.2 (2H, d, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_2\text{Ph})\text{COOH}$), 4.2 (1H, q, $\text{S-CH}(\text{CH}_3)$), 4.8 (1H, m, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_2\text{Ph})\text{COOH}$), 6.4–7.1 (2H, m, ArH), 7.2–7.4 (2H, m, ArH), 7.5–7.9 (3H, m, ArH), 8–8.1 (2H, m, ArH), 9.9 (1H, brs, CONH), 10.6 (1H, s, COOH)
5d	CH_3	CH_2SH	1713, 1665, 2506, 3325	1.0 (3H, d, CH_3), 2.74 (1H, s, $\text{NHCH}(\text{CH}_2\text{SH})\text{COOH}$), 3.3 (2H, m, $\text{HCH}(\text{CH}_2\text{SH})\text{COOH}$), 4.21 (1H, q, $\text{S-CH}(\text{CH}_3)$), 7.1–7.3 (2H, m, ArH), 7.5 (1H, d, ArH), 7.77–7.9 (1H, d, ArH), 9.9 (1H, brs, CONH), 10.4 (1H, s, COOH)

Table-2 (contd.)

5e	CH ₃ CH ₂ - CH ₂ - CH ₃	1710, 1662, 2400, 3300	0.94 (3H, t, CH ₃), 1.0 (3H, d, CH(CH ₃)), 1.3-1.35 (4H, m, 2 × CH ₂), 4.1 (1H, q, S-CH(CH ₃)), 4.65 (1H, m, NHCH(CH ₃)-COOH), 7.1-7.34 (2H, m, ArH), 7.4-7.5 (1H, d, ArH), 7.7-7.8 (1H, d, ArH), 9.7 (1H, brs, CONH), 10.45 (1H, s, COOH)
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Table 3. Screening data of some compounds for probable activities on the basis of Computer program PASS⁷

Activities	R = H, R' = H	R = H, R' = CH ₃	R = H, R' = CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	R = H, R' = CH ₂ SH
Angiogenesis inhibitor	0.798	-	0.788	0.788
NMDA receptor glycine site agonist	0.631	-	0.563	0.563
Chemoprotective	0.631	0.371	0.676	0.676
Autoimmune disorders treatment	0.627	0.650	0.681	0.681
Antiosteoporotic	0.574	-	0.539	0.529
Tyrosine phosphatase inhibitor	0.627	0.329	0.633	0.663
Bone disease treatment	0.555	-	0.507	0.507
Antitoxic	0.656	0.516	0.495	0.495
Antiseborrheic	0.576	0.764	0.655	0.655

Synthesis of 2-(benzothiazol-2-yl)acetamido acetic acid (4a) :

To the solution of glycine (0.1 mmol) in 25 ml 4 N NaOH, 0.2 mmol of compound 2 was added and the reaction mixture cooled to 0-5 °C in an ice bath. Further 25 ml 4 N NaOH was added to above mixture and stirred vigorously for 3 h, then extracted with ether, acidified

with conc. HCl. On keeping overnight the solid obtained was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol.

Similarly, the compounds 5a-e were synthesized by adopting similar methodology. The physical and spectral data of compounds 4a-e and 5a-e have been incorporated in Tables 1 and 2.

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